

D7.9

Second report on dissemination and final MaX workshop

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D7.9 Second report on dissemination and final MaX workshop

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1 Executive Summary

This Document summarizes the dissemination actions put in place by the MaX CoE in the second 18 months of activity (from March 2017 to August 2018). MaX dissemination includes initiatives aimed at researchers and academia, as well as dedicated actions targeting industrial end-users.

Scientific achievements have been published in internationally recognised, peer-reviewed scientific journals, typically of very high impact. The efforts towards researchers, graduate students and potential academic users has also taken broad advantage of typical Conference and Workshop channels. MaX members have given an impressive number of invited and contributed talks to conferences, workshops, and seminars, covering all range of subjects related to the CoE activity: from methodological developments, to improvement of HPC performances and technology exploitation, to cutting edge computational studies of scientific test cases.

The above initiatives represent the bulk of the dissemination actions of MaX, together with a few broader-impact actions and an increased social media presence through web portal, newsletter, twitter.

MaX strong training activities, described in deliverable D6.4 for the same period, also represented a valuable and impactful channel of dissemination. Dissemination actions specifically directed to industry --especially individual meetings and the industry-specific website-- are described in deliverable D5.4 on industrial outreach, which covers the time period M16-M36 (January 2017 – August 2018).

2 Participation to Conferences, Workshops, Seminars

MaX members have systematically and actively participated in the major domain specific (electronic structure and materials science) and high performance computing (HPC) conferences. Moreover, MaX researchers have been invited to give seminars and lectures in a number of different environments. In these occasions they have presented MaX results, or their specific research results including the role played by MaX.

2.1 List of invited talks, lectures, and seminars

A list of invited talks given by MaX members in international conferences about MaX topics is given in the following (List 1). The high number of talks shows the commitment of scientists to disseminate MaX knowledge and results, in Europe and beyond. Subjects covered range from

methodological and algorithmic developments, to scientific software implementation in HPC environment, to the actual exploitation of the MaX flagship codes (together with their new functionalities and performance improvements) in scientific case studies. In Table 1 a (partial) list of contributed talks or posters is also given.

List 1. Invited talks, lectures, and seminars.

(The format given is Title. Speaker, Event, Place. Date)

(a) About MaX

Business model design.

Carlo Daffara (Cloudweavers), Cooperation on exploitation strategies among CoEs, Amsterdam Schiphol airport Conference Center (NL). 23/03/2017

Designing Materials with HPC.

Guido Chiarotti (CNR Nano), Amsterdam Schiphol airport Conference Center (NL). 23/03/2017

MaX presentation to EMMC and stakeholders.

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano), European Materials Modeling Council International Workshop 2017 (EMMC), Vienna (AT). 5-7/04/2017

MaX – Materials design at the eXascale.

Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), Workshop of the Spanish “Supercomputación y e-Ciencia” Network, Madrid (Spain). 26/04/2017

MaX CoE activities presentation.

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano), Paris Meeting on Computational Materials: Challenges & Opportunities, with Directors of Centres in the world, Paris (FR). 31/05 - 02/06/2017

Materials Discovery, Data on Demand & Open Science.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), ISC17, Frankfurt (DE). 16-22/06/2017

Exascale Challenges: The view from MaX.

Carlo Cavazzoni (CINECA), E-CAM Extreme-Scale Workshop, Barcellona (ES). 06/07/2017

MARVEL, MaX, and materials design

Nicola Marzari (EPFL) at E-CAM Workshop from the atom to the material, Cambridge (UK). 18/09/2017

PRACE exascale use cases.

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano), Contribution to the document as resulting action of the workshop PRACE-GEANT workshop. 13/10/2017

Workshop Preparing EuroHPC roadmap. User requirements and technology offer for next generation HPC.

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano), Euro HPC Workshop 2017, Brussels (BE). 05/12/2017

New HPC architectures landscape and impact on code developments.

Carlo Cavazzoni (CINECA), HPC CRESCO6 launch @ENEA, Portici (IT). 30/05/2018

(b) About pilot codes

Quantum Espresso performance on Xeon PHI, comparison with Xeon E52697v4.

Carlo Cavazzoni (CINECA), KNL Workshop, CINECA, Bologna (IT). 22/03/2017

First AiiDA Workflow with FLEUR for Core-level Spectroscopy.

Jens Broeder (Jülich), DPG 2017 Dresden, Dresden (DE). 22/03/2017

1) *GW, ARPES, and lifetimes: a theory overview.*

2) *Yambo, parallelization strategies and performance.*

Andrea Ferretti (CNR Nano), Hands-on Tutorial on Excited State Spectroscopy: GW and BSE using the Yambo code, CECAM, Lausanne (CH). 24-28/04/2017

Fleur with AiiDA, steps towards material design, how to accelerate your work.

Jens Broeder (Jülich), All electron DFT with FLEUR - a Hands-on Tutorial, Jülich (DE). 08/05/2017

FLEUR goes HPC.

Uliana Alekseeva (Jülich), All electron DFT with FLEUR - a Hands-on Tutorial, Jülich (DE). 08/05/2017

Managing Computational Science: The ADES model and the AiiDA infrastructure.

Sebastian Huber (EPFL), International Workshop of Materials Genome Infrastructure and Materials Design, Institute of Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing (PRC). 13/06/2017

Computational Crystallography with quantum ESPRESSO (a few years later).

Paolo Giannozzi (UniUD), CECAM Discussion Meeting on Quantum Crystallography, Nancy (FR). 19/06/2017

Managing computational materials science in the high-throughput era: The ADES model and the AiiDA infrastructure.

Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL), TERATEC2017, École Polytechnique, Paris (FR). 28/06/2017

Quantum ESPRESSO: introduction to the code and parallelization schema.

Pietro Bonfà (CINECA), Material science codes on innovative HPC architectures: Targeting Exascale, Cineca, Bologna (IT). 05/12/2017

New developments in the Quantum ESPRESSO software distribution for quantum simulations at the nanoscale.

Paolo Giannozzi (UniUD), From experiments to theory & models: a computational challenge for Biophysics, Roma Tor Vergata University (IT). 05/12/2017

1) *The AiiDA platform for computational materials science.*

2) *AiiDA from a user's perspective: HPC and HTC stories.*

Antimo Marrazzo (EPFL), Materials Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale, CINECA, Bologna (IT). 06/12/2017

Materials Cloud: An Open Portal for Computational Materials Science.

Snehal Kumbhar (EPFL), EUDAT Conference - Putting the EOSC vision into practice, Porto (PT). 22/01/2018

Automating materials discovery using AiiDA: provenance concepts and some use cases.

Leonid Kahle (EPFL), LLNL - Computational Materials Science group meeting, Livermore (US). 12/02/2018

Introduction to AiiDA.

Leonid Kahle (EPFL), MARVEL School on Variationally Enhanced Sampling, Lugano (CH). 16/02/2018

Performance Evolution of the FLEUR Code.

Uliana Alekseeva (Juelich), NIC Symposium 2018, Jülich (DE). 22/02/2018

Experiences parallelizing Fleur.

Uliana Alekseeva (Juelich), 3rd Workshop on Parallel Programming Models - Productivity and Applications, Aachen (DE). 15/03/2018

Managing computational materials science in the high-throughput era: AiiDA and the Materials Cloud.

Spyros Zoupanos (EPFL), Seminário do Departamento de Física dos Materiais e Mecânica, Instituto de Física, Universidade de São Paulo (BR). 23/03/2018

What can a good SIESTA do for you?

Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam (NL). 01/05/2018

Using AiiDA to accelerate discovery in Materials Science: some examples.

Davide Campi (EPFL), CECAM Fleur Tutorial, Juelich Research Center, Juelich, (DE). 08/05/2018

Porting Quantum ESPRESSO to GPUs: Lessons Learnt and Remaining Challenges.

Pietro Bonfà (CINECA), PASC18, Basel (CH). 03/07/2018

Advances in SIESTA: New Functionalities, Domain Libraries, and Scripting Interfaces.

Alberto García (ICMAB), Electronic structure theory with numeric atom-centred basis functions, Technical University of Munich (DE). 09/07/2018

Quantum ESPRESSO: Real World Application, Performance and Optimization on the Marconi Supercomputer.

Carlo Cavazzoni (CINECA), Intel Webinar. 12/07/2018

Tasks, Challenges and Objectives for the SIESTA code

Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), MaX Hackathon, Barcelona Supercomputing Centre, Barcelona (ES). 16/07/2018

Comparing Efficiency of Iterative Eigenvalue Solvers: the Quantum ESPRESSO experience.

Stefano de Gironcoli (SISSA). Workshop on "Computational Methods for Eigenvalue Problems" in Changchun (PRC). 14-17/08/2018

Comparing Efficiency of Iterative Eigenvalue Solvers: the Quantum ESPRESSO experience.

Stefano de Gironcoli (SISSA). Workshop on "Solving or Circumventing Eigenvalue Problems in Electronic Structure Theory" in Richmond (Virginia, USA). 15-17/08/2018

Hybrid Parallelization and Performance Optimization of the FLEUR Code: New Possibilities for All-Electron Density Functional Theory.

Uliana Alekseeva (Juelich), Euro-Par 2018 Conference, Turin (IT). 29/08/2018

(c) About computational science

The Times They Are A-Changin'

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), TCM Seminar, Cambridge (GB). 02/03/2017

Adventures in Flatland

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Graphene Center, Cambridge (GB). 03/03/2017

Car and Parrinello meet Green and Kubo: simulating atomic heat transport from equilibrium ab-initio molecular dynamics.

Stefano Baroni (SISSA), March Meeting of American Physical Society, New Orleans, (US). 13-17/03/2017

HERE AND NOW: The intersection of computational science, quantum-mechanical simulations, and materials science

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), APS March Meeting, New Orleans (USA). 13/03/2017

Electronic and Optical properties of Graphene Nanoribbons.

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano), APS March Meeting 2017, New Orleans (US). 16/03/2017

Layered and 2D materials: electronic properties and structural instabilities from first principles

Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), Institute of Functional Nano & Soft Materials, Soochow University, Soochow (PRC). 16/03/2017

Materials Design and Discovery

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), CNR Foresight Meeting, Rome (IT). 23/03/2017

Computational Exfoliation of all known Inorganic Materials

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Graphene 2017, Barcelona (ES). 28/03/2017

Electron and Optical Spectroscopies of Graphene Nanoribbons on Au(111): Insights from Ab-Initio Calculations.

Andrea Ferretti (CNR Nano), EuSpec meeting on: Electron and Absorption spectroscopies: coordination between experiment and theory, Krakow (PL). 04-05/04/2017

A new age for computational materials science.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), ChE-602 - Recent Events in Energy seminar series, Sion (CH). 13/04/2017

Realistic Simulations of Complex Materials.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), CECAM School on advanced computing of excited state properties in solids and nanostructures using Yambo, Lausanne (CH). 24/04/2017

The GW method: general implementations and common approximations.

Daniele Varsano (CNR Nano), Cecam School: Advanced computing of excited state properties in solids and nanostructures with Yambo, CECAM-HQ-EPFL, Lausanne (CH). 25/04/2017

Excitations in quasi-1D systems: Conceptual and computational developments

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano)

A multiscale approach to the simulation of the optical properties of complex molecules in solution.

Stefano Baroni (SISSA)

Workshop on Spectroscopy and Dynamics of Photoinduced Electronic Excitations, Trieste (IT). 8-12/05/2017

The ADES Model.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), International workshop on machine learning and data analytics in advanced metals processing, Manchester (GB). 22/05/2017

Thermal conductivity of 2D materials from first principles

Sergio Illera (ICN2), European Materials Research Society (E-MRS). Spring Meeting. Strasbourg (FR). 23/05/2017

Multiple Exciton Generation in Silicon Nanocrystals.

Ivan Marri (CNR Nano), Nanomeeting 2017, Minsk (BY). 30/05/2017

MARVEL

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Computational Materials: Challenges and Future Opportunities, Paris (FR). 31/05/2017

Materials Discovery, Data on Demand, and Open Science.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), ISC 2017, Frankfurt (DE). 24/06/2017

Materials Discovery, Data on Demand, and Open Science.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), EPFL IBM Day, Lausanne (CH). 28/06/2017

Computational Discovery in the 21st Century

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), PASC 17, Lugano (CH). 26-28/06/2017

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lpj2R_A7lb0&feature=youtu.be

Adventures in Flatland.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Colloquium, Department of Physics, University of Rome Sapienza (IT). 04/07/2017

Thermal conductivity de 2D materials from first principles

Sergio Illera (ICN2), XXXIII Annual meeting of the Reference Network in Theoretical and Computational Chemistry, ICIQ, Tarragona (ES). 06/07/2017.

Car and Parrinello meet Green and Kubo: simulating atomic heat transport from equilibrium ab-initio molecular dynamics.

Stefano Baroni (SISSA), XXIX IUPAP Conference on Computational Physics, Paris (FR). 9-13/07/2017

Why is DFT like tinder?

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), SUNCAT Summer School, Stanford, Palo Alto (USA). 14/08/2017

Illuminating nanosystems at surfaces.

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano), 33rd European Conference on Surface Science (ECOSS33), Szeged (HU). 27/08-1/09/2017

Pump and Probe experiments described by first principles non-equilibrium Green's functions.

Davide Sangalli (CNR-ISM), CMD 26. Symposium 22: theoretical spectroscopy, Groeningen (NL). 05/09/2017

Materials Discovery, Data on Demand, and Open Science.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), CECAM School on big-data driven materials science, Lausanne (CH).

11/09/2017

Computational Design and Discovery of Novel Materials.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), MAPEX Symposium 2017 – “MATERIALS INFORMATICS” , Bremen (DE). 15/09/2017

Silicon and Germanium nanostructures for optoelectronic and photovoltaic applications: ab-initio results.

Ivan Marri (CNR Nano), EMRS fall meeting 2017, Warsaw (PL). 18/09/2017

Coherent electron transport through molecular junctions.

Andrea Ferretti (CNR Nano), Ab initio modelling in solid state chemistry 2017, London (UK). 18-22/09/2017

Materials Discovery, Data on Demand, and Open Science.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Future Energy Conference, Eindhoven (NL). 20/09/2017

Open Science Platform

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), EPFL Open Science in Practice, Lausanne (CH). 25/09/2017

Managing Computational Science: the importance of data provenance.

Sebastian Huber (EPFL), Materials Research and Data Science Conference, NIST/CHiMaD/GaTech, Rockville MD (US). 26/09/2017

Parallel Programming for HPC.

Ivan Girotto (ICTP), Master in High-Performance Computing, ICTP, Trieste (IT). 1/10/2017

Carbon Nanotubes as Excitonic Insulators.

Daniele Varsano (CNR Nano), FISMAT 2017, Trieste (IT). 02/10/2017

Transport from first-principles.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), EPFL-MPG Science Day, Lausanne (CH). 05/10/2017

Collective Phenomena In Boltzmann Transport.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), CPMD2017, Tsukuba (JP). 18/10/2017

2D, or not 2D.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Department of Physics, DTU, Lyngby (DK). 27/10/2017

Workflows and data integration: vision and sustainability.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), EMMC Workshop on Interoperability in Materials Modelling –

IntOP2017, Cambridge (GB). 07/11/2017

Electronic instabilities in 2D materials and their interfaces

Miguel Pruneda (ICN2), 1st International Workshop Series "Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience", IMDEA Nanociencia, Madrid (ES). 30/11/2017

1) GW, ARPES, and lifetimes: a theory overview. 2) Electron and Optical Spectroscopies of Graphene Nanoribbons on Au(111): Insights from Ab-Initio Calculations.

Andrea Ferretti (CNR Nano), Materials Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale, CINECA, Bologna (IT). 4-6/12/2017

Role of quantum confinement in anatase nanosheets.

Daniele Varsano (CNR Nano), Psi-k workshop 2D layered materials for opto-electronics: a theoretical/computational perspective, Rome (IT). 18/12/2017

Electronic instabilities and metallic grain boundaries in dichalcogenides

Miguel Pruneda (ICN2), Psi-k Workshop: 2D layered materials for opto-electronics: a theoretical/computational perspective, CECAM Node Simul, Rome (IT). 18/12/2017.

High-throughput search of novel 2d materials for electronic and optoelectronic applications.

Davide Campi (EPFL), PSI-K Workshop "2D layered materials for optoelectronics: a theoretical/computational perspective", Rome (IT). 18/12/2017

New developments in exact exchange calculations with plane waves.

Ivan Carnimeo, FISMAT 2017, Trieste (IT). 10/01/2018

The power of not thinking: materials' discovery in the 21st century.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Colloquium, Depart of Physics, Martin Luther University. Halle (DE). 25/01/2018

Layered and 2D materials: electronic properties and structural instabilities from First Principles

Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati - SISSA, Trieste (IT). 01/02/2018

Ab initio Green-Kubo simulation of thermal transport in liquids, glasses, and strongly anharmonic solids.

Stefano Baroni (SISSA), ICN2 Severo Ochoa International Conference 2018, Barcelona (ES). 15-16/02/2018

Electronic structure codes on KNL, profiling and benchmarking results.

Pietro Bonfà (CINECA), IXPUG Annual Spring Conference 2018, Cineca, Bologna (IT). 05/03/2018

Electronic Structure Codes on KNL: Structural, electronic and optical properties of graphene Nanoribbons.

Andrea Ferretti (CNR Nano), IXPUG Annual Meeting 2018, CINECA, Bologna (IT). 5-7/03/2018

Integration of high- throughput, provenance and dissemination: the case of novel 2D materials.
Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL), APS March Meeting 2018, Los Angeles, CA (US). 09/03/2018

2D, or not 2D.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Semi-plenary talk at the annual meeting of the German Physical Society. Berlin (DE). 11/03/2018

A room-temperature and switchable Kane-Mele quantum spin Hall insulator.
Antimo Marrazzo (EPFL), DPG Berlin 2018, Berlin (DE). 12/03/2018

High-throughput screening of 2d materials for electronic and optoelectronic applications.
Davide Campi (EPFL), DPG 2018, Berlin (DE). 12/03/2018

Layered and 2D materials: electronic properties and structural instabilities from first principles
Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), Nanospain 2018, Bilbao (ES). 14/03/2018

Where Do We Come From? What Are We? Where Are We Going?.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Invited seminar at the Fritz-Haber Institut. Berlin (DE). 06/04/2018

Electron and Optical Spectroscopies of Graphene Nanoribbons on Au(111): Insights from Ab-Initio Calculations.

Andrea Ferretti (CNR Nano), School of Mathematics and Physics, Queen's University, Belfast (UK). 11/04/2018

Layered and 2D materials: electronic properties and structural instabilities from first principles
Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), SP2 Network Kickoff Meeting, Madrid (ES). 12/04/2018

Spin-orbit coupling studies of materials: some examples

Roberto Robles (ICN2), Donostia International Physics Center. San Sebastián (ES). 20/04/2018

To see a world in a grain of sand.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Colloquium, Department of Physics. Pavia (IT). 03/05/2018

Ab-initio approach and Database for Fitting High resolution XPS Spectra.

Jens Broeder (Juelich), The 15th ETSF Young Researchers' Meeting 2018, Hamburg (DE). 04/05/2018

What I cannot compute, I do not understand: fathoming heat (and charge) transport from the struggle to simulate it.

Stefano Baroni (SISSA), Physics Department of the Bilkent University, Ankara (TK). 9/05/2018

Modelling materials using quantum mechanics and digital computers: the plane-wave pseudopotential way.

Density-functional perturbation theory: response functions, phonons, and all that.

Stefano Baroni (SISSA), QUANTUM ESPRESSO Workshop, Penn State University (US). 21-25/05/2018

Mystery On the enhancement of thermal properties of graphene nanofluids

Francesca Costanzo (ICN2), Simulations (and theory) in Physical chemistry: an international Kermesse in Paris, Paris (France), 28-29/05/2018

The importance of High Performance Computing to accelerate Material Discovery.

Stephan Mohr (BSC), Workshop "High performance computing for next generation nanomaterials & nanodevices engineering", Catalan Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (ICN2), Barcelona (ES). 30-31/05/2018

Discovering two-dimensional materials from high-throughput computational exfoliation of experimentally known compounds.

Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL), PRACE-MaX tutorial on high-throughput computations: general methods and applications using AiiDA, CINECA, Bologna (IT). 31/05/2018

Fast screening of solid-state lithium-ion conductors.

Leonid Kahle (EPFL), PRACE-MaX tutorial on high-throughput computations: general methods and applications using AiiDA, CINECA, Bologna (IT). 01/06/2018

Calculations of electronic structures in crystals and Quantum ESPRESSO Tutorial

Paolo Giannozzi (UniUd), Erice School on Quantum Crystallography, Erice (IT). 01/06/2018

Two-dimensional materials from high-throughput computational exfoliation of experimentally known compounds.

Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL), Swiss Nanoconvention 2018, ETH Zürich (CH). 06/06/2018

2D, or not 2D.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Invited seminar, IBM Research Labs. Zurich (CH). 06/06/2018.

The power of not thinking.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Invited seminar, CC2AI conference. Lausanne (CH). 14/06/2018.

Materials modelling and discovery: the high-performance computing way.

Stefano Baroni (SISSA), proESOF TESI International Meeting on Open Access and Impact of Research Infrastructures, Trieste (IT). 18-19/06/2018

Carbon nanotube as excitonic insulator.

Daniele Varsano (CNR Nano), Department Seminar, University of Tor Vergata, Roma (IT). 22/06/2018

Advanced Path Integral Techniques.

Michele Ceriotti (EPFL), Path Integral Quantum Mechanics: From the Basics to the Latest Developments, EPFL, Lausanne, (CH). 26/06/2018

Discovering novel materials: the convergence of HPC, HTC, and HPDA.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Invited seminar, ISC, Frankfurt (DE). 27/06/2018.

Layered and 2D materials: electronic properties and structural instabilities from first principles

Pablo Ordejón (ICN2), Nanotech France 2018, Paris (FR). 28/06/2018

Hybrid Quantum Anomalous Hall Effect at graphene-oxide interfaces

Zeila Zanolli (ICN2), Université catholique de Louvain, Institute of Condensed Matter and Nanosciences, Nanoscopic Physics, Louvain-la-Neuve (Belgium). 28/06/2018

Materials Cloud: A platform for Open Materials Science.

Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL), PASC18 Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing, Basel, (CH). 04/07/2018

Free as a bird – new vistas in the materials' landscape.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), David Pettifor's memorial symposium. Oxford (UK). 10/07/2018

Materials Discovery in the 21st century and New solutions to old equations.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Masterclass at the Thomas Young Centre, The London Centre for the Theory and Simulation of materials, London (UK). 13/07/2018

<https://www.thomasyoungcentre.org/events/tyc-masterclass-prof-nicola-marzari/>

Density Functional Perturbation Theory with localized atomic orbitals

Miguel Pruneda (ICN2), Seminar at the Computational Science Division at Lawrence Berkeley Lab, Berkeley (USA). 17/7/2018.

Anomalous screening and excitonic insulator in nanotubes.

Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano), NT 18, Peking University, Beijing (PRC). 19/07/2018

Computational design and discovery of novel materials.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Plenary talk, ACEMD18. Sydney (Australia). 24/07/2018

2D or not 2D, this is the question.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), CAMD 2018 Summer School, Elsinore (DK). 14/08/2018.

Carrier multiplication in Si-NCs: ab-initio results

Ivan Marri (CNR Nano), IMRC-2018, Cancun (Mexico), 20/08/2018

Computational design and discovery of novel materials.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Swiss Physical Society, Lausanne (CH). 29/08/2018

Theoretical prediction of excitonic instability in reduced dimensionality systems

Daniele Varsano (CNR Nano), Cecam workshop: Excitonic insulator: New perspectives in long-range interacting systems CECAM-HQ-EPFL, Lausanne (CH). 3-5/09/2018

Carbon Nanotubes as excitonic insulators

Daniele Varsano (CNR Nano), Nanoinnovations 2018 - Faculty of Civil and Industrial Engineering of "Sapienza" University of Rome, Rome (IT). 11-14/09/2018.

Coherent electron transport through molecular junctions.

Andrea Ferretti (CNR Nano), Ab initio modelling in solid state chemistry 2018, London (UK). 17-21/09/2018

(d) others

Digital Day2017: Panel II – How Europe can regain leadership in HPC.

Thomas Schulthess (ETH Zurich), Digital Day 2017, Rome (IT). 23/03/2017

<https://youtu.be/2y5LWCZLluc>

Materials Discovery, Data on Demand, and Open Science

Individual talk by Prof. Nicola Marzari (EPFL) during visit of Sir Mark Walport, UK Government Chief Scientific Adviser, Lausanne (CH). 30/03/2017

The power of not thinking.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL) at Seminar: Department of Materials, University of Milano Bicocca (IT).

19/05/2017

Talk by Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano) - in Session 5: *High performance computing, big data & super-connectivity* - about the links between European Data infrastructure (HPC, data storage, connectivity) and the European Science Cloud, Brussels (BE). 12/06/2017

<https://webcast.ec.europa.eu/european-open-science-cloud-summit#>

Computational Discovery in the 21st Century.

Public talk by Nicola Marzari (EPFL) @ PASC 2017, Lugano (CH). 26-28/06/2017

Video available here

<https://insidehpc.com/2017/07/video-computational-discovery-21st-century/>

Time to reach exascale.

Radio Interview by Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano). Radio 24. 28/06/2017

Interview available here:

<http://www.radio24.ilsole24ore.com/programma/smart-city/supercalcolo-vicina-soglia-esascale-100104-gSLAvILZMC>

Advanced capabilities for materials modelling with Quantum ESPRESSO.

Article in Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter. Interview by Tom Sharp to Paolo Giannozzi (UniUD) to find out more in his own words about the recent progress and advances on this software. 30/10/2017

<https://jphysplus.iop.org/2017/10/30/advanced-capabilities-for-materials-modelling-with-quantum-espresso/>

The 2017 European HPC Handbook.

CoEs section by Elisa Molinari (CNR Nano). 14/11/2017

IXPUG (Intel eXtreme Performance Users Group) Annual Spring Conference 2018 @CINECA, Bologna (IT). 5-8/03/2018

<https://eventi.cineca.it/en/events/ixpug-annual-spring-conference-2018>

Agenda of the meeting with MaX partners talks and contributions:

<https://www.ixpug.org/events/spring2018>

Interview to Scott Auerbach about his vision on why “*What MARVEL is doing is a dream come true for researchers in the field*”. In particular, he discussed the big advantages that AiiDA and Materials Cloud can give to researchers in the community. 26/04/2018

<http://nccr-marvel.ch/highlights/2018-04-what-marvel-is-doing-is-a-dream-come-true>

New materials to rethink the world.

Public speech in Teatro Eliseo, Rome (IT), by Nicola Marzari (EPFL) on quantum simulation, materials design and future perspectives. 07/05/2018

Industry-Academia Day.

Dissemination event dedicated to the simulation of advanced materials properties.
Talk by Nicola Marzari (EPFL) at Liège University (BE). 16/05/2018

Computational design and discovery of new materials: challenges and opportunities.

Dissemination event. Talk by Nicola Marzari (EPFL) at Liège University (BE). 17/05/2018

ISC High Performance 18.

Fabrizio Magugliani (E4). Booth at the exhibition promoting MaX CoE.
Frankfurt (DE). 24-28/06/2018

From waste to resource: a research perspective.

Nicola Marzari (EPFL), Invited round table, World Materials Forum. Nancy (FR). 29/06/2018.

(e) selected posters

Date	Name of the Event	Place	Title of presentation
20/3/17	DPG 2017 Dresden	Dresden (DE)	Aiida Workflows with FLEUR for X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy.
23/3/17	Optical Nanospectroscopy III	Rome (IT)	Pump and Probe experiments from first principles in bulk silicon.
12/4/17	Workshop: Ultra-fast phenomena in quantum physics: a challenge for theory & experiment	Lausanne (CH)	Pump and Probe experiments from first principles in bulk silicon.
22/5/17	Third International Workshop on Models and Data for Plasma-Material Interaction in Fusion Devices (MoD-PMI 2017)	Forschungszentrum Jülich (DE)	AiIDA Workflows with FLEUR for X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy.
7/11/17	3rd BNC-b PhD meeting, ICMAB-CSIC	Barcelona (ES)	SIESTA code integration with AiIDA high-throughput framework for modern computational tasks.
29/1/18	MaX International Conference "Materials Design Ecosystem at the Exascale: High-Performance and High-Throughput Computing"	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	SIESTA interface to AiIDA
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Linear Response with Density Functional Perturbation Theory in SIESTA.
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Performance evolution of FLEUR
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Overview of SIESTA developments within the MaX project
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Excited states in TiO2
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	A non-conventional use of AiIDA: validation and performance evaluation of Quantum ESPRESSO on different HPC architectures.
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	The AiIDA- FLEUR package
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Thermo_pw: a FORTRAN driver for Quantum ESPRESSO routines
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	AiIDA -Automated interactive infrastructure and database for computational science
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Spin—Orbit implementation by means of fully separable Kleinman—Bylander pseudopotential formalism under atomic orbital basis in SIESTA code
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Prediction of a large -gap and switchable Kane-Mele quantum spin Hall insulator
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	GW calculations without massive use of empty states: a new tool in Yambo
29/1/18	MaX International Conference	ICTP, Trieste (IT)	Carbon nanotubes as excitonic insulators
22/2/18	NIC Symposium 2018	Jülich (DE)	Performance Evolution of the FLEUR Code
14/3/18	DPG Frühjahrstagung 2018	Berlin (DE)	The FLAPW code FLEUR: scaling and performance im- provements on the route towards the exascale.
14/3/18	DPG 2018	Berlin (DE)	The AiIDA-FLEUR package, how you can predict XPS spectra with it.
4/7/18	PASC18 Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing	Basel (CH)	Materials Cloud: A platform for Open Materials Science
6/7/18	PASC18 Platform for Advanced Scientific Computing	Basel (CH)	AiIDA: a simulation platform with full provenance support and flexible workflows

(f) women in science

- *103rd Congress of the Italian Physics Society, Trento (IT) 11-15/09/2017*
Elisa Molinari took part to the round table “Fisica: femminile singolare” (Physics: feminine singular).

- Researchers proudly participated to the Twitter campaign called #WeAreHPC organized and promoted by Women in HPC. In an effort to ensure the greater HPC sector is inclusive and welcoming to all communities, Women in HPC launched an online campaign during SC17. https://twitter.com/women_in_hpc

○

- At MaX_CoE we celebrated the “*International Day of Women and Girls in Science*” with a dedicated twitter communication aimed to support women and girls’ professional

and vocational path every day. Many outstanding women scientists work in our CoE and, hopefully, many others will join.

<https://twitter.com/hashtag/InternationalDayofWomenandGirlsInScience?src=hash>

<https://twitter.com/hashtag/WomenInScience?src=hash>

-
- *34th International Conference on the Physics of Semiconductors (ICPS)*.
Montpellier (FR) July 29 - August 03, 2018
Elisa Molinari was part of the International Advisory Committee and actively collaborated to the organization of the *Women in Science and technology Session* during the ICPS Conference.

2.2 List of publications

A list of publications authored by MaX members is given below. All publications acknowledge MaX support (e.g., “We acknowledge support from the EU Centre of Excellence MaX - Materials Design at the Exascale” (Grant No. 676598)” or alike).

2018

1. Bonds, lone pairs, and shells probed by means of on-top dynamical correlations
S. Pittalis, D. Varsano, A. Delgado, C.A. Rozzi
European Physical Journal B, 2018, 91, p. 187
DOI: [10.1140/epjb/e2018-90143-4](https://doi.org/10.1140/epjb/e2018-90143-4)
Impact (Web of science). Journal IF 2017: 1.536
2. Prediction of a Large-Gap and Switchable Kane-Mele Quantum Spin Hall Insulator
A. Marrazzo, M. Gibertini, D. Campi, N. Mounet, N. Marzari

Physical Review Letters, 2018, 120, 117701

DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevLett.120.117701](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.120.117701)

Impact (Web of science). Journal IF 2017: 8.839

3. ELSI: A unified software interface for Kohn–Sham electronic structure solvers
V. W. Yu, F. Corsetti, A. Garcia, W. P. Huhn, M. Jacquelin, W. Jia, B. Lange, L. Lin, J. Lu, W. Mi, A. Seifitokaldani, A. Vazquez-Mayagoitia, C. Yang, H. Yang, V. Blum
Computer Physics Communications, 2018, 222, pp 267-285
DOI: [10.1016/j.cpc.2017.09.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2017.09.007)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 3.748
4. Linear scaling DFT calculations for large tungsten systems using an optimized local basis
S. Mohr, M. Eixarch, M. Amsler, M. J. Mantsinen, L. Genovese
Nuclear Materials and Energy, 2018, 15, pp 64-70
DOI: [10.1016/j.nme.2018.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2018.01.002)
5. Quantum Crystallography: Current Developments and Future Perspectives
A. Genoni, L. Bučinský, N. Claiser, J. Contreras-García, B. Dittrich, P. M. Dominiak, E. Espinosa, C. Gatti, P. Giannozzi, J.-M. Gillet, D. Jayatilaka, P. Macchi, A. Ø. Madsen, L. Massa, C. F. Matta, K. M. Merz Jr., P. N. H. Nakashima, H. Ott, U. Ryde, K. Schwarz, M. Sierka, S. Grabowsky
Chemistry - A European Journal, 2018, 24, pp 10881-10905
DOI: [10.1002/chem.201705952](https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.201705952)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 5.16
6. The PSML format and library for norm-conserving pseudopotential data curation and interoperability
A. García, M. J. Verstraete, Y. Pouillon, J. Junquera
Computer Physics Communications, 2018, 227, pp 51-71
DOI: [10.1016/j.cpc.2018.02.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2018.02.011)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 3.748
7. Two-dimensional materials from high-throughput computational exfoliation of experimentally known compounds
N. Mounet, M. Gibertini, P. Schwaller, D. Campi, A. Merkys, A. Marrazzo, T. Sohier, I. E. Castelli, A. Cepellotti, G. Pizzi, N. Marzari
Nature Nanotechnology, 2018, 13, pp 246–252
DOI: [10.1038/s41565-017-0035-5](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-017-0035-5) [OA]
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 37.49
8. Breathing bands due to molecular order in CH₃NH₃PbI₃
M. Wierzbowska, J. J. Meléndez, D. Varsano
Computational Materials Science, 2018, 142, pp 61-71
DOI: [10.1016/j.commatsci.2017.10.039](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2017.10.039)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 2.53

9. Bright Electroluminescence from Single Graphene Nanoribbon Junctions
M. C. Chong, N. Afshar-Imani, F. Scheurer, C. Cardoso, A. Ferretti, D. Prezzi, G. Schull
Nano Letters, 2018, 18 (1), pp 175–181
DOI: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b03797](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b03797)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.08
10. Clean Os(0001) electronic surface states: A first-principle fully relativistic investigation
A. Urru, A. Dal Corso
Surface Science, 2018, 671, pp 17-26
DOI: [10.1016/j.susc.2018.01.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susc.2018.01.006)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 1.997
11. Ultrafast Charge Migration in XUV Photoexcited Phenylalanine: A First-Principles Study Based on Real-Time Nonequilibrium Green's Functions
E. Perfetto, D. Sangalli, A. Marini, G. Stefanucci
Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters, 2018, 9 (6), pp 353–1358
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jpcclett.8b00025](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.8b00025)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 8.709
12. Charge Separation in Donor–C₆₀ Complexes with Real-Time Green Functions: The Importance of Nonlocal Correlations
E. Viñas Boström, A. Mikkelsen, C. Verdozzi, E. Perfetto, G. Stefanucci
Nano Letters, 2018, 18 (2), pp 785–792
DOI: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b03995](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b03995)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.08
13. Koopmans-compliant functionals for extended system: band gaps of semiconductors and insulators
N.-L. Nguyen, N. Colonna, A. Ferretti, N. Marzari
Physical Review X, 2018, 8, 2, 021051
DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevX.8.021051](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevX.8.021051)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 14.385
14. Ferromagnetic and Antiferromagnetic Coupling of Spin Molecular Interfaces with High Thermal Stability
G. Avvisati, P. Mondelli, P. Gargiani, C. Cardoso, D. Varsano, A. Ferretti, M.G. Betti
Nano Letters, 2018, 18, pp 2268-2273
DOI: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b04836](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b04836)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.08
15. Theory and Ab Initio Computation of the Anisotropic Light Emission in Monolayer Transition Metal Dichalcogenides
H. Y. Chen, M. Palummo, D. Sangalli, M. Bernardi
Nano Letters, 2018, 18, pp 3839-3843

DOI: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.8b01114](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.8b01114)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.08

16. An ab-initio approach to describe coherent and non-coherent exciton dynamics

D. Sangalli, E. Perfetto, G. Stefanucci, A. Marini

European Physical Journal B, 2018, 91, 172

DOI: [10.1140/epjb/e2018-90126-5](https://doi.org/10.1140/epjb/e2018-90126-5)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 1.536

17. Optical and electronic properties of 2H–MoS₂ under pressure: Revealing the spin-polarized nature of bulk electronic bands

M. Brotons-Gisbert, A. Segura, R. Robles, E. Canadell, P. Ordejón, and J. F. Sánchez-Royo

Physical Review Materials, 2018, 2, 054602

DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevMaterials.2.054602](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevMaterials.2.054602)

18. Spin Proximity Effects in Graphene/Topological Insulator Heterostructures

K. Song, D. Soriano, A. W. Cummings, R. Robles, P. Ordejón, and S. Roche

Nano Letters, 2018, 18, 2033

DOI: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b05482](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b05482)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.08

19. Spin-Crossover in an Exfoliated 2D Coordination Polymer and Its Implementation in Thermochromic Films

S. Suárez-García, N. N. Adarsh, G. Molnár, A. Bousseksou, Y. Garcia, M. M. Dîrtu, J.

Saiz-Poseu, R. Robles, P. Ordejón, D. Ruiz-Molina

ACS Applied Nano Materials, 2018, 1, 2662

DOI: [10.1021/acsanm.8b00341](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.8b00341)

20. Mechanisms behind the enhancement of thermal properties of graphene nanofluids

M.R. Rodriguez-Laguna, A. Castro-Alvarez, M. Sledzinska, J. Maire, F. Costanzo, B. Ensing, M. Pruneda, P. Ordejon, C.M.Sotomayor Torres, P. Gomez-Romero, E. Chavez-Angel.

Nanoscale, 2018, 10, 15402-15409

DOI: [10.1039/c8nr02762](https://doi.org/10.1039/c8nr02762)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 7.233

21. First principles analysis of the CDW instability of single-layer 1T-TiSe₂ and its evolution with charge carrier density

B. Guster, E. Canadell, M. Pruneda, P. Ordejón

2D MATERIALS, 2018, 5, 025024

DOI: [10.1088/2053-1583/aab568](https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1583/aab568)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 7.042

22. A Massively Parallel Algorithm for the Approximate Calculation of Inverse p-th Roots of Large Sparse Matrices
M. Lass, S. Mohr, H. Wiebeler, R. D. Kuhne, C. Pleschl.
Conference Proceedings PASC18, 2018
23. Hybrid Parallelization and Performance Optimization of the FLEUR Code: New Possibilities for All-Electron Density Functional Theory
U. Alekseeva, G. Michalicek, D. Wortmann, S. Blügel
In: Aldinucci M., Padovani L., Torquati M. (eds) Euro-Par 2018: Parallel Processing. Euro-Par 2018.
Lecture Notes in Computer Science, 2018, 11014
DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-96983-1_52](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96983-1_52)

2017

24. Lamb shift of the Dirac cone of graphene
P. M. M. C. de Melo, A. Marini
Europhysics Letters, 2017, 116 (4)
DOI: [10.1209/0295-5075/116/43001](https://doi.org/10.1209/0295-5075/116/43001)
25. Probing optical excitations in chevron-like armchair graphene nanoribbons
R. Denk, A. Lodi-Rizzini, S. Wang, M. Hohage, P. Zeppenfeld, J. Cai, R. Fasel, P. Ruffieux, R. Berger, Z. Chen, A. Narita, X. Feng, K. Mullen, R. Biagi, V. De Renzi, D. Prezzi, A. Ruini, A. Ferretti
Nanoscale, 2017, 9, 18326
DOI: [10.1039/C7NR06175G](https://doi.org/10.1039/C7NR06175G)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 7.233
26. Addressing the Environment Electrostatic Effect on Ballistic Electron Transport in Large Systems: A QM/MM-NEGF Approach
G.T. Feliciano, C.Sanz-Navarro, M.D. Coutinho-Neto, P. Ordejon, R.H. Scheicher, and A.R. Rocha
Journal of Physical Chemistry B, 2018, 122, 485.
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b03475](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.7b03475)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 3.146
27. Optical properties of periodic systems within the current-current response framework: Pitfalls and remedies
D. Sangalli, J. A. Berger, C. Attaccalite, M. Grüning, P. Romaniello
Physical Review B, 2017, 95 (15)
DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevB.95.155203](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.95.155203)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 3.813
28. Improvements on non-equilibrium and transport Green function techniques: The next-generation transiesta

- N. Papior, N. Lorente, T. Frederiksen, A. García, M. Brandbyge
Computer Physics Communications, 2017, 212, pp. 8-24
DOI: [10.1016/j.cpc.2016.09.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2016.09.022)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 3.748
29. Role of Quantum-Confinement in Anatase Nanosheets
D. Varsano, G. Giorgi, K. Yamashita, M. Palummo
Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters, 2017, 8 3867
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jpcllett.7b01717](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.7b01717)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 8.709
30. Lattice dynamics and thermophysical properties of h.c.p. Re and Tc from the quasi-harmonic approximation
M. Palumbo, A. Dal Corso
Physica Status Solidi b, 2017, 254 (9)
DOI: [10.1002/pssb.201700101](https://doi.org/10.1002/pssb.201700101)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 1.729
31. Unconventional Current Scaling and Edge Effects for Charge Transport through Molecular Clusters.
V. Obersteiner, G. Huhs, N. Papior, E. Zojer
Nano Letters, 2017, 17 (12), pp 7350–7357
DOI: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b03066](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b03066)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.08
32. Ab Initio Calculations of Ultrashort Carrier Dynamics in Two-Dimensional Materials: Valley Depolarization in Single-Layer WSe₂
A. Molina-Sánchez, D. Sangalli, L. Wirtz, A. Marini
Nano Letters, 2017, 17 (8), pp 4549–4555
DOI: [10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b00175](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b00175)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.08
33. Efficient Computation of Sparse Matrix Functions for Large-Scale Electronic Structure Calculations: The CheSS Library
S. Mohr, W. Dawson, M. Wagner, D. Caliste, T. Nakajima, L. Genovese
Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation, 2017, 13 (10), pp 4684–4698
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jctc.7b00348](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.7b00348)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 5.399
34. Graphene-based synthetic antiferromagnets and ferrimagnets
P. Gargiani, R. Cuadrado, H. B. Vasili, M. Pruneda, M. Valvidares
Nature Communications, 2017, 8, 699
DOI: [10.1038/s41467-017-00825-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-00825-9)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.353

35. Complexity Reduction in Large Quantum Systems: Fragment Identification and Population Analysis via a Local Optimized Minimal Basis
S. Mohr, M. Masella, L. E. Ratcliff, L. Genovese
Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation, 2017, 13 (9), pp 4079–4088
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jctc.7b00291](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.7b00291)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 5.399
36. How To Identify Plasmons from the Optical Response of Nanostructures
R. Zhang, L. Bursi, J. D. Cox, Y. Cui, C. M. Krauter, A. Alabastri, A. Manjavacas, A. Calzolari, S. Corni, E. Molinari, E. A. Carter, F. J. García de Abajo, H. Zhang, P. Nordlander
ACS Nano, 2017, 11 (7), pp 7321–7335
DOI: [10.1021/acsnano.7b03421](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nano.7b03421)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 13.709
37. Accurate thermal conductivities from optimally short molecular dynamics simulations
L. Ercole, A. Marcolongo, S. Baroni
Scientific Reports, 2017, 7, 15835
DOI: [10.1038/s41598-017-15843-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-15843-2)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 4.122
38. A Performance Study of Quantum ESPRESSO's PWscf Code on Multi-core and GPU Systems
J. Romero, E. Phillips, G. Ruetsch, M. Fatica, F. Spiga, P. Giannozzi
In: *High Performance Computing Systems. Performance Modeling, Benchmarking, and Simulation. PMBS 2017. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 2017, 10724
DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-72971-8_4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-72971-8_4)
39. Carbon nanotubes as excitonic insulators
D. Varsano, S. Sorella, D. Sangalli, M. Barborini, S. Corni, E. Molinari, M. Rontani
Nature Communications, 2017, 8 1461
DOI: [10.1038/s41467-017-01660-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-01660-8)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 12.353
40. Advanced capabilities for materials modelling with Quantum ESPRESSO
P. Giannozzi, O. Andreussi, T. Brumme, O. Bunau, M. Buongiorno Nardelli, M. Calandra, R. Car, C. Cavazzoni, D. Ceresoli, M. Cococcioni, N. Colonna, I. Carnimeo, A. Dal Corso, S. de Gironcoli, P. Delugas, R. A. DiStasio Jr, A. Ferretti, A. Floris, G. Fratesi, G. Fugallo, R. Gebauer, U. Gerstmann, F. Giustino, T. Gorni, J. Jia, M. Kawamura, H-Y Ko, A. Kokalj, E. Küçükbenli, M. Lazzeri, M. Marsili, N. Marzari, F. Mauri, N. L. Nguyen, H-V. Nguyen, A. Otero-de-la-Roza, L. Paulatto, S. Poncé, D. Rocca, R. Sabatini, B. Santra, M. Schlipf, A. P. Seitsonen, A. Smogunov, I. Timrov, T. Thonhauser, P. Umari, N. Vast, X. Wu and S. Baroni
Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter, 2017, 29 (46), 465901-465931
DOI: [10.1088/1361-648X/aa8f79](https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-648X/aa8f79)

Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 2.617

41. FePc adsorption on the moire superstructure of graphene intercalated with a Co layer
G. Avvisati, S. Lisi, P. Gargiani, A. Della Pia, O. De Luca, D. Pacile', C. Cardoso, D. Varsano, D. Prezzi, A. Ferretti, M.G. Betti
J. Phys. Chem. C, 2017, 121 (3), 1639-1647
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b09875](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.6b09875)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 4.536
42. Many-body correlations and coupling in benzene-dithiol junctions.
T. Rangel, A. Ferretti, V. Olevano, G.-M. Rignanese
Physical Review B, 2017, 95, 115137
43. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevB.95.115137](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.95.115137)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 3.813
44. A posteriori metadata from automated provenance tracking: Integration of AiiDA and TCOD
A. Merkys, N. Mounet, A. Cepellotti, N. Marzari, S. Gražulis, G. Pizzi
Journal of Cheminformatics, 2017, 9
DOI: [10.1186/s13321-017-0242-y](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-017-0242-y)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017:
Journal IF 2017: 4.220
45. Theoretical $S_1 \leftarrow S_0$ absorption energies of the anionic forms of oxyluciferin by Variational Monte Carlo and Many Body Green's Function Theory.
E. Coccia, D. Varsano and L. Guidoni
Journal of Chemical Theory and Comput., 2017, 13, 4357
DOI: [10.1021/acs.jctc.7b00505](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.7b00505)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 5.399
46. First Principle Studies of B and P Doped Si Nanocrystals.
I. Marri, E. Degoli, S. Ossicini
Physica Status Solidi A, 2017, 215, 3
DOI: [10.1002/pssa.201700414](https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.201700414)
Impact (Web of Science). Journal IF 2017: 1.795
47. Doped and codoped silicon nanocrystals: The role of surfaces and interfaces.
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3 MaX Events

3.1 MaX Conference, Trieste (IT), January 29-31, 2018

On January 29-31, 2018 in Trieste (IT) at ICTP, the International Max Conference “Materials Design Ecosystem at the Exascale: High-Performance and

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High-Throughput Computing” took place. The general focus of the conference, organized by MaX was on the scientific advances in computational materials research, as well as future developments in the exascale perspective.

Main topics of the conference were:

- Scientific advances in materials research exploiting high-performance computing
- High-throughput computing for materials discovery
- New avenues from data analytics / artificial intelligence in materials science
- Trends in high performance computing and codesign towards exascale
- New algorithms for first principles simulations.

The conference was organized by CNR, SISSA, ICTP and about 110 people attended the 3 days meeting organised in several thematic sessions, all based on the contributions from 32 invited speakers coming from within and outside the network, and poster sessions.

The program is shown below. Complete information, including the presentations, the conference poster, and the participant list are available at the conference website <http://indico.ictp.it/event/8004/overview>.

A webpage in the MaX website was dedicated to the event (<http://www.max-centre.eu/international-conference-2018/>) and linked to a dedicated page in the ICTP website (<http://indico.ictp.it/event/8004/overview>). This hosts all the meeting presentations and the video recording of each talk.

The conference was covered by live tweeting on MaX’s Twitter account @max_center2 and a conference hashtag was created #MaxConf2018.

The conference was the perfect stage for the award ceremony of the “MaX Prize for flagship code applications” that were assigned to:

1. *Zeila Zanolli*, RWTH Aachen, for her research on “Ab initio design of new materials for spintronics applications”, codes used Siesta & Fleur;
2. *Anu Baby*, University of Milano Bicocca, for her research on “Adsorption of Organic Molecules on Metals: A Computational Materials Science Approach”, code used Quantum ESPRESSO;
3. *Nicolas Mounet et al.*, EPFL STI IMX THEOS, for their research on “Novel two-dimensional materials from high-throughput computational exfoliation of experimentally known compounds”, code used AiiDA.

One of the MaX Prize recipients, Zeila Zanolli with the Prize scientific committee.

The MaX International Advisory Board meeting was held in Trieste just after the conference.

The complete program of the meeting is reported below.

MaX INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Day 1: Monday, January 29

8.00	Registration and administrative formalities (Leonardo Building - Lobby)
9.00	Welcome Elisa Molinari and Fernando Quevedo (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)
	Trends in High Performance Computing (9.15-10.30) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)
9.15	Thomas Sterling Stagnation at Moore’s Nano scale Barrier and an HPC Architecture Reboot

9.40	Dirk Pleiter	Fenix: Realising a new paradigm for collaborative supercomputing research infrastructures
10.05	Carlo Cavazzoni	New HPC architectures landscape and impact on code developments, the view of MaX
10.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	Advances in Electronic Structure I (10.45-12.40) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)	
11.00	Stefano Baroni	Ab-initio Green-Kubo simulation of thermal transport in liquids and glasses: a challenge to theoretical physics and to HPC technology
11.25	Pablo Ordejon	On the enhanced thermal transport properties of graphene nanofluids
11.50	Boris Kozinsky	New energy materials from data-driven computations of transport properties
12.15	Marivi Fernandez-Serra	Understanding water/solid functional interfaces for photocatalysis and electrochemical applications
12.40	<i>Lunch</i>	
	Codesign I (14.30-16.10) (Adriatico Guesthouse – Kastler Lecture Hall)	
14.30	Massimiliano Fatica	Quantum Espresso on GPU accelerated systems
14.55	Anton Kozhevnikov	GPU acceleration of plane-wave codes using SIRIUS library
15.20	Luca Benini	Scaling Performance in Power-limited HPC Systems
15.45	Pietro Bonfa'	Performance prediction for QuantumESPRESSO
16.10	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	Codesign II (16.40-17.30) (Adriatico Guesthouse – Kastler Lecture Hall)	
16.40	Filippo Spiga	Arm role in the co-design of the next generation HPC platforms
17.05	Luigi Brochard	Co-designing Energy Efficient Systems
17.30	POSTER SESSION with refreshment (17.30-19.30) (Adriatico G. – Kastler Lecture Hall - Lower level)	

Day 2: Tuesday, January 30

	New Algorithms (8.30-10.00) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)	
8.30	Lin Lin	Variational formulation for finding Wannier functions with entangled band structure
8.55	Ivan Carnimeo	Hartree-Fock exchange with localized orbitals for fast and efficient calculations with the Quantum ESPRESSO code
9.20	Stephan Mohr	Efficient Computation of Sparse Matrix Functions for Large-Scale Electronic Structure Calculations: The CheSS Library
9.45	MaX PRIZE CEREMONY	
10.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	Advances in Electronic Structure II (10.30-12.10) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)	
10.30	Stefan Blugel	Spin-orbit interaction — a path to topological matter in real and moment space

10.55	Zeila Zanolli	Spintronics at the interface
11.20	Anu Baby	Adsorption of Organic Molecules on Metals: A Computational Materials Science Approach
11.45	Maria Clelia Righi	Ab initio study of lubricant materials
12.10	<i>Lunch</i>	
14.00	Advances in Electronic Structure III (14.00-15.15) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)	
14.00	Davide Sangalli	Pump and probe experiments from first principles
14.25	Luca Grisanti	Predicting the color of natural dyes using quantum mechanics, statistical physics, and high-performance computing
14.50	Deborah Prezzi	Light emission from ultranarrow graphene nanoribbons: edge and termini effects
15.15	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	Advances in Electronic Structure IV (15.45-16.35) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)	
15.45	Thierry Deutsch	Adaptive and localized basis functions for linear scaling, large systems and complex QM simulations
16.10	Jürg Hutter	MP2, RPA and GW within the Gaussian and Plane Waves Method
17.00	POSTER SESSION with drinks (17.00-19.00) (Adriatico G. – Kastler Lecture Hall - Lower level)	

Day 3: Wednesday, January 31

	High-throughput in Material Science (8.30-10.35) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)	
8.30	Stefano Sanvito	High-throughput electronic structure theory: are all calculations useful?
8.55	Nicolas Mounet	Two-dimensional materials from high-throughput computational exfoliation of experimentally known compounds
9.20	Karsten W. Jacobsen	Computational screening of solar energy materials
9.45	Geoffroy Hautier	Finding the needle in the haystack: Materials discovery through high-throughput ab initio computing and data mining
10.10	Leopold Talirz	Materials Cloud, a Platform for Open Materials Science
10.35	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	Data Analytics in Material Science (11.05-12.45) (Leonardo Building – Budinich Lecture Hall)	
11.05	Alessandro Curioni	Data driven R&D for Materials: Cognitive Discovery
11.30	Roberto Car	Deep Neural Networks and Molecular Dynamics
11.55	Juan F. Carrasquilla	A machine learning perspective on the many-body problem in classical and quantum physics
12.20	David Wilkins	Symmetry Matters: Learning Scalars and Tensors in Materials and Molecules
12.45	Closing Remarks	

3.2 MaX Hackathon, Barcelona (ES). July 16-20, 2018

The 2018 MaX Hackathon, organised by CNR, UniUD, ICN2, BSC, JUELICH, EPFL, and ICTP offered an informal brainstorming environment and practical coding sessions on the MaX flagship codes (Quantum ESPRESSO, Siesta, Fleur, Yambo, AiiDA), including:

- Working groups active in the development of each flagship code, e.g. targeting the development of new features, performance improvements, performance portability to new architectures including GPUs, benchmarking and profiling.
- Advanced training for developers on selected topics (novel parallel paradigms, emerging MPI and OpenMP features/standards, support of GPUs & HW heterogeneity, HDF5 and parallel IO).
- Transversal coding activities (eg parallel IO, support of common electronic structure formats, GPU support).

The Hackathon was advertised through the psi-k network, the pw_forum, the CINECA mailing list and the MaX newsletter mailing list. 45 people attended the Hackathon from inside and outside the community. Detailed information about this event are available in the D6.4 in the section training events.

A complete Twitter coverage of the event was done with the hashtag #MaXHackathon with more than 20 Tweets and several retweets. Some presentations were transmitted live, see for example https://twitter.com/max_center2/status/1018847602153082880.

3.3 Social media dissemination activities

This second period of MaX has witnessed a major increase in dissemination activities via social media. These have been supported by:

- a **dedicated website**, www.max-centre.eu, updated with all the information, events, news regarding the MaX project, the codes developments, etc.

Here the statistics regarding the website (updated 31/08/2018)

	Visitors	Visits
Last 365 days	66.357	184.369
Total	103.101	284.469

- a **Twitter account** @max_center2 with 435 followers

Here some statistics regarding the twitter account (updated 31/08/2018)

	Tweets visualizations	Account visualizations
Last 365 days	223.712	10.333

- The **MaX periodic newsletter** has been a regular channel for MaX dissemination and communication philosophy. MaX newsletter brings to the subscribers (745 users) all the latest news about MaX network, its codes, its research and latest development.

First issue: 20/04/2017

Second issue: 08/08/2017

Third issue: 24/11/2017

Fourth issue: 13/07/2018

All the newsletters are available in the MaX website page: <http://www.max-centre.eu/newsletter/>

at

4 Dissemination towards industry

Dissemination towards industry is described in a separate deliverable: D5.4 “Report on the industrial outreach activities and CoE services”.

5 Dissemination via training

MaX dissemination has been also greatly impacted by the training/tutorial events organized as part of WP6 activities. During these events, methodological and algorithmic developments related to the MaX flagship codes are presented, technically described, and taught within hands-on sessions. This provides an ideal environment for disseminating opportunities and recent

outcomes of the CoE toward the trainees and their research groups. In addition, we have found that trainees are among the best ambassadors of MaX and its codes in a broader context.

The impressive list of MaX training events is reported in Deliverable D6.4 “Second Report on training courses/workshops”. Among them 12 schools/tutorials/workshops directly organized by MaX, 23 ‘training through research’ visits in MaX laboratories, and a large number of additional lectures and modules. We refer the reader to that document for further details.